

NEWSLETTER

ISSUE 2, AUGUST 2023

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1. INTERVIEW WITH THE BIOSYSMO COORDINATOR

We had the privilege to talk with Dr. Lila Otero, the coordinator of the BIOSYSMO project at IDENER, to delve into the fascinating world of biotechnology and sustainable systems modeling. Dr. Otero brings a wealth of expertise in the field, combining her passion for innovation with her dedication to creating a more sustainable future. In this interview, we explore the groundbreaking work of the BIOSYSMO project, its goals, challenges, and the impact it can have on various industries.

What is the BIOSYSMO project and what are its objectives?

BIOSYSMO is a European collaborative project that aims to develop green and sustainable technologies for remediation of soil, water and sediments polluted with different hazardous contaminants. For this, we focus on bioremediation technologies, which use the power of microorganisms and plants to degrade and uptake pollutants from the environment. Our ambition is to improve bioremediation systems by focusing on the synergies within microbial communities and between these communities and plants. We want to develop bioremediation systems that are not only effective to remove recalcitrant pollutants but are also gentle with the environment so we can revitalize degraded sites into safe and clean areas.

Which are the main innovations and benefits from the BIOSYSMO project?

The main innovations of the BIOSYSMO project are precisely the focus on understanding and strengthening the synergies within microbial communities and between these communities and plants. Different partners approach this question from an experimental methodology by studying

1. INTERVIEW WITH THE BIOSYSMO COORDINATOR

associations between plants and microorganisms, developing artificial microbial communities, testing novel bioelectrochemical systems to boost the microbial activity or applying genetic engineering methods to both plants and bacteria. Moreover, in BIOSYSMO we want to advance in the application of digital tools in bioremediation and for that we are developing and applying different computational methods and models to understand and improve the biosystems.

What are the impacts that can be expected from this project?

Understanding and strengthening the synergies within bioremediation systems is crucial for improving their efficiency and reliability. This is a key factor in establishing bioremediation as a feasible and sound alternative to physicochemical remediation methods, even in challenging scenarios, whether used independently or in combination with other treatment technologies. In this way, BIOSYSMO will contribute to achieve the objectives of the European Zero Pollution Action Plan to halt and prevent pollution, to meet end goals and regulatory criteria at contaminated sites and to protect and restore Europe's ecosystems and biodiversity.

2. BIOSYSMO APPLICATIONS

Step into the exciting world of BIOSYSMO, an ambitious and cutting-edge research project aiming to revolutionize environmental remediation through innovative biotechnological approaches.

BIOSYSMO, unites a diverse consortium of experts in bioremediation, plant biology, microbial ecology, and environmental engineering. Together, we are committed to tackling the most pressing challenges posed by soil and water contamination, propelling sustainable remediation strategies forward.

Our comprehensive endeavor involves the application of 5 distinct approaches, each meticulously tailored to target specific environmental pollutants and optimize remediation efficiency. Below, we delve into the details of these applications.

“Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria-assisted water phytoremediation” harnesses the potential of Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR) to facilitate water phytoremediation in floating systems. By inoculating bacterial strains on roots or carriers, the project aims to monitor various remediation effects on both plant and water parameters, contributing to eco-friendly solutions for contaminated water sources.

APPLICATION 1

APPLICATION 2

“Combined poplar-microbe biosystems for soil phytoremediation” explores the integration of new traits from microorganisms into hybrid poplar lines, enhancing their capabilities for endophyte root colonization and resistance to organic pollutants. The project will assess the modified poplars' tolerance to metal and organic pollutants while evaluating their potential for colonization by selected bacterial and fungal strains, paving the way for advanced phytoremediation approaches.

2. BIOSYSMO APPLICATIONS

“Estuarine sediment microbial-assisted phytoremediation” delves into the remediation of estuarine sediment by improving saltmarsh plants and their natural microbiome potential to effectively remove both organic and inorganic contaminants. This approach aims to evaluate the effectiveness of bioaugmented plant biosystems to tackle mixed pharmaceuticals and metals contamination.

APPLICATION 3

“Treatment of (ground) water with BES and BES-phytoremediation approaches” extends the project’s scope beyond phytoremediation, harnessing the power of Bioelectrochemical Systems (BES) reactors for (ground)water remediation. By implementing microstructured electroactive microbial biofilms on electrodes, the project seeks to process contaminated water, targeting a range of pollutants including organic and inorganic contaminants.

APPLICATION 4

“Soil biostimulation and bioaugmentation” aims to remediate soil contamination by applying genetically improved strains in soil microcosms. Through bioaugmentation and biostimulation strategies, the project will optimize biodegradation processes by adjusting physicochemical factors such as soil temperature, salinity, pH, moisture content, and nutrient composition.

APPLICATION 5

3. BIOSYSMO PRESENCE AT EVENTS

GLOBAL SOIL BIODIVERSITY CONFERENCE

On 13-15 March 2023, University of Burgos (UBU) participated in the 3rd Global Soil Biodiversity Conference, which took place in Dublin, Ireland. The conference centered around the theme of 'Science as a Basis for the Sustainable Use and Conservation of Soil Biodiversity.' During the event, UBU presented the BIOSYSMO Project, highlighting our involvement in clustering activities and showcasing our communication tools and platforms. For more information about the conference, you can visit the event's website [HERE!](#)

PHYTOSUDOE FINAL CONFERENCE

On 30-31 March 2023, University of Burgos (ICCRAM - UBU) participated in the final conference of Phy2SUDOE. At the event, colleagues from UBU presented the progress and findings of their work under the BIOSYSMO Project during a poster session held on March 31st.

For more details about the conference, you can [PRESS HERE!](#)

7TH INT. SYMPOSIUM ON ENVIRONMENTAL BIOTECHNOLOGY AND ENGINEERING

The University of Burgos made a significant mark at the 7th International Symposium on Environmental Biotechnology and Engineering, held in Marseille, France, from 22nd to 26th May. Aqib Hassan Ali Khan, member of the UBU team, left a lasting impression by presenting an engaging poster and delivering a captivating oral presentation focused on their innovative phytoremediation trial. The symposium served as a vital platform for knowledge exchange and collaboration, reaffirming their commitment to sustainable solutions in environmental preservation. For more details [CLICK HERE!](#)

3. BIOSYSMO PRESENCE AT EVENTS

SOIL BIOREMEDIATION SEMINAR

Dr. Lila Otero-Gonzalez, our coordinator from IDENER, gave a talk on 26th April 2023 at the Soil Bioremediation Seminar organized by Universidad del País Vasco/Euskal Herriko Unibertsitatea's Master's Degree in Environmental Engineering and Management. The lecture focused on the "Importance of studying microbiomes for remediating contaminated sites and its application in the BIOSYSMO Project."

CIIMAR GIVING LECTURES AT THE MSc COURSES OF FACULTY OF SCIENCE OF UNI. OF PORTO

On April 12, 2023, Marisa Almeida, a distinguished expert from CIIMAR, delivered an insightful and informative lecture as part of the MSc course in Environmental Sciences and Technologies at the Faculty of Science of the University of Porto in Porto, Portugal. Moreover, Marisa also enclosed information about BIOSYSMO during the lecture for the MSc in Plants Biotechnology at Faculty of Science of University of Porto, on May 17, 2023. Her expertise in the field undoubtedly enriched the learning experience of the attending students, providing valuable insights into the latest developments and challenges in environmental sciences and technologies. The event served as an inspiration for the students, further fueling their passion for environmental stewardship and the pursuit of sustainable solutions for our planet's well-being.

IMAB'23 CONFERENCE

CIIMAR organised the IMAB 2023 conference, on April 19-20 2023, while also actively participating in it, presenting the BIOSYSMO work in a poster presentation. Representatives from CIIMAR, JSI and UBFC also made keynote presentations where they addressed several bioremediation issues including those being dealt within BIOSYSMO. The conference focused on exploring novel advancements in the chemical, molecular, and biogeochemical mechanisms of microbialmediated processes, with a specific emphasis on their connection to metals.

4. BIOSYSMO OUTREACH ACTIVITIES

3-Minute Thesis Competition

We proudly highlight the achievements of our colleagues, Alberto Soto Cañas and Alondra Jiménez Pérez from ICCRAM – University of Burgos. On May 12th, they participated in the highly anticipated 3-Minute Thesis Competition, presenting their groundbreaking research directly related to the BIOSYSMO Project. Alberto Soto Cañas delivered a compelling presentation on bioremediation systems, emphasizing enhanced pollutant removal through synergies. Alondra Jiménez Pérez showcased her work on cutting-edge biosystems for targeted pollutant transformation and uptake in various environmental matrices. Their impressive performances in the competition exemplify our team's dedication to excellence and innovative research in the BIOSYSMO Project.

For more check [HERE!](#)

Pint of Science

Blanca Velasco Arroyo and Rocío Barros from the University of Burgos actively took part in the Pint of Science – Burgos event on May 23rd. During the event, they shared intriguing findings from the BIOSYSMO Project, highlighting the significance of understanding microbiomes in pollutant degradation within soil and the role of plants in removing metals from water. For further

details, you can explore the event [AGENDA](#) and find additional information [HERE!](#)

5. BIOSYSMO PUBLICATIONS

Two more publications are already available in open access journals by University of Burgos and UBFC – Université Bourgogne-Franche-Comté

New Publication:
"Pharmaceuticals in Water: Risks to Aquatic Life and Remediation Strategies"

"Pharmaceuticals in Water: Risks to Aquatic Life and Remediation Strategies" in Hydrobiology Journal

"The potential of microorganisms as biomonitoring and bioremediation tools for mercury-contaminated soils" in Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety Journal.

6. CLUSTERING WORKSHOP

CLUSTERING WORKSHOP WITH EU BIOREMEDIATION PROJECTS AT BIOREMID23

We are thrilled to have participated in the GREENER Project Conference and Cluster Workshop, held in Muttenz, Switzerland, as a satellite event of the BioRemid 2023 conference—an event that brought together a diverse and passionate community of bioremediation experts. Among the notable participants was the BIOSYSMO Project consortium, comprising a collaborative group of researchers and experts in the field of bioremediation. This event provided an exceptional and intellectually stimulating platform for experts in bioremediation technologies from across Europe to convene, share knowledge, and present their research on mitigating environmental pollution through innovative biological approaches.

The dissemination corner at the workshop proved to be a captivating and informative feature, showcasing the outcomes of seven cluster projects (GREENER, BIOSYSMO, SYMBIOREM, MIBIREM, NYMPHE, ELECTRA, EiCLAR). Attendees had the opportunity to attend engaging presentations that highlighted the progress achieved within these projects. This initiative not only fostered awareness of the potential of bioremediation but also served as an inspiration for future collaborative endeavors within the bioremediation community.

It should be highlighted that two European Commission (EC) officers attended the event, whose warm and

6. CLUSTERING WORKSHOP

insightful introduction set the tone for the event, encouraging fruitful discussions and knowledge sharing among the participants. The BIOSYSMO Project coordinator's presentation provided a comprehensive overview of their research and illustrated the consortium's dedication to sustainable and eco-friendly solutions.

For those eager to delve deeper into the world of bioremediation and explore the wealth of knowledge presented at the conference, additional details can be found at the official BioRemid 2023 conference website: www.bioremid.com

The workshop recording provides some visualized highlights of the workshop and can be found [HERE!](#)

MEET THE BIOSYSMO CONSORTIUM

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